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PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE WORK OF MARITIME SPECIALISTS

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Summary. Panov B. V. **PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE WORK OF MARITIME SPECIALISTS.** - *Ukrainian Research Institute for Medicine of Transport of the Ministry of Health Care of Ukraine, Odesa; e-mail: nymba.od@gmail.com.* The aim: to analyze the results of the studies of the Research Institute for Medicine of Transport (Odesa) in the field of psychophysiology of seafarers. In analyzing the operator activity of maritime specialists, it is crucial to evaluate the flows of incoming, processed, and outgoing information (observation, control, and monitoring). Important characteristics include not only quantitative measures but also qualitative parameters such as complexity and relevance. The workloads for different groups of marine specialists (ship engineers, navigators, deck crew, etc.) have been investigated. It has been revealed that a high degree of strain is typically characteristic of the marine specialists work, especially under the conditions of long multi-month voyages. Thus, alongside fitness medical examinations, preliminary and periodic psychophysiological examination should be implemented as a crucial preventive measure aimed at preserving sailors' health and providing individually oriented rehabilitation (medical and socio-psychological) during off-voyage periods. Targeted medical selection and psychoprophylactic measures open the prospect of actively managing adaptation processes under extreme sailing conditions, contributing to health preservation, reduction of psycho-emotional tension, prevention of injuries, and maritime safety.

Key words: fitness medical examination, psycho - emotional tension, prevention of injuries, maritime safety.

Реферат. Панов Б. В. **ПСИХОФІЗІОЛОГІЧНІ АСПЕКТИ ПРАЦІ МОРСЬКИХ СПЕЦІАЛІСТІВ.** **Мета:** проаналізувати результати досліджень Науково-дослідного інституту медицини транспорту (Одеса) в галузі психофізіології моряків. При аналізі операторської діяльності морських спеціалістів вирішальним є оцінка потоків вхідної, обробленої та вихідної інформації (спостереження, контроль та моніторинг). Важливими характеристиками є не лише кількісні показники, а й якісні параметри, такі як складність та актуальність. Досліджено робоче навантаження різних груп морських спеціалістів (суднових механіків, штурманів, палубної команди тощо). Виявлено, що високий ступінь напруження є типовою рисою роботи морських спеціалістів, особливо в умовах тривалих багатомісячних рейсів. Таким чином, поряд з медичними оглядами на предмет придатності, слід впроваджувати попереднє та періодичне психофізіологічне обстеження як вирішальний профілактичний захід, спрямований на збереження здоров'я моряків та забезпечення індивідуально орієнтованої реабілітації (медичної та соціально-психологічної) у міжрейсовий період. Цілеспрямований медичний відбір та психопрофілактичні заходи відкривають перспективу активного управління процесами адаптації в екстремальних умовах плавання, сприяючи збереженню здоров'я, зниженню психоемоційної напруги, запобіганню травматизму та безпеки праці.

Ключові слова: професійний медичний відбір, психо-емоційне напруження, профілактика травмування, безпека морської праці.

The Ukrainian Research Institute of Transport Medicine in Odessa traces its history back to 1975, when a Laboratory of Maritime Hygiene was established within the Research Institute of Hygiene of Water Transport of the Ministry of Health of the former USSR. Later, this laboratory was transformed into a branch and eventually into the All-Union Research Institute of Hygiene of Water Transport. Since 1991, after becoming subordinated to the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, the institute has acquired its present name and expanded its scope to cover other modes of transport.

Throughout its history, the institute has been home to distinguished scientists who made significant contributions to various branches of medicine. One of the important directions of research has been the study of psychophysiological aspects of maritime professionals' activity. A substantial contribution to this field was made by renowned scholars - Prof. Eduard M. Psiadlo, DSc (Biology), and Prof. Leonid M. Shafran, MD, DSc. The results of their research were reflected in monographs, scientific articles, and in the development of the Psychophysiological Certification System (SPAS). This system has been successfully applied in the work of the Center for Psychophysiological Expertise for employees working under harmful and hazardous conditions - not only in the transport sector, but also in other areas of industry.

The present article includes research materials from our eminent colleagues, E.M. Psiadlo and L.M. Shafran, which were not fully analyzed during their lifetime, as well as the author's own investigations. With this work, the author seeks to pay tribute to the grateful memory of his senior colleagues, who are no longer with us.

Professiographic Analysis of Maritime Specialists' Activities. In analyzing the operator activity of maritime specialists, it is crucial to evaluate the flows of incoming, processed, and outgoing information (observation, control, and monitoring). Important characteristics include not only quantitative measures but also qualitative parameters such as complexity and relevance. An analysis of the data presented in Table 1 showed that ship engineers experience the largest and most intensive informational workload. Within the sensory field of ship operators, there is a considerable number of information display devices (on average 243–461), along with 149–184 control elements. The most heavily engaged cognitive functions include sensory-perceptual abilities, short-term and working memory, most aspects of attention, as well as operational-dynamic and simultaneous thinking. Notably, one-third of the control elements are located outside the operators' motor field, creating conditions for significant static strain combined with hypokinesia and prolonged localized muscular effort.

Table 1

Number of Information Display Devices and Control Elements

Types of Devices and Control Elements	Name of Devices	Number of Devices and Control Elements	
		Bridge	Engine Room
Information Display Devices (<i>sensory field</i>)	Screens	2-3	--
	Light indicators	180-220	270-395
	Scale instruments	19-35	25-89
	Digital counters	4-12	7-36
	Mnemonic diagrams	2-3	2-9
	Loudspeaker communication	4-8	4-6
	Total	243	461
Control Elements (<i>motor field</i>)	Manipulators	2-5	2-8
	Levers	2-20	0-1
	Tumblers	27-35	44-78
	Switches	41-86	33-67
	Buttons	36-72	108-148
	Steering wheels	1	--
	Microphones	4-8	1
	Total	149	184
Grand total:	412	645	

For navigators, the greatest workload is associated with the necessity of continuous monitoring and reading data from radar and computer screens, along with the reception and processing of visual and verbal information. The balance between “active” functions and “passive” functions (operational waiting) fluctuates widely depending on the specific conditions of the voyage.

The character of labor during navigational watches on long ocean passages is marked by a high degree of monotony, particularly at night. Contributing factors include scarcity of external stimuli, limited visual field, and sensory deprivation, further intensified by insufficient lighting, repetitive noise and vibration from the ship and marine environment, isolation of the watch crew, and hypokinesia. Under these conditions, the decreased influence of the ascending reticular activating system must be counterbalanced by the operator’s volitional efforts to maintain operational readiness. Conversely, complex navigational and hydrometeorological conditions lead to heightened activity and psychoneural mobilization (up to labor intensity categories 5–6), which is more typical of short-sea voyages.

Table 2

Number of Informational Signals Processed per Hour by Maritime Specialists (E.M. Psiadlo, L.M. Shafran)

Profession	Signals	Object	Process	Time	Location	Action	Density
Navigator	<u>32</u>	*	*	*	*		<u>128</u>
	84	*	*	*	*	*	420
Engineer	<u>28</u>	*	*	*			<u>84</u>
	68	*	*	*	*	*	340
Electromechanic	<u>23</u>	*	*				<u>46</u>
	43	*	*		*	*	172
Motorman	<u>24</u>	*	*			*	<u>72</u>
	41	*	*		*	*	164
Sailor–Helmsman	<u>22</u>	*	*			*	<u>66</u>
	49	*	*	*	*	*	294

Notes: Numerator – calm sailing conditions; denominator – high-intensity sailing conditions.

* - indicates presence of the criterion.

Labor intensity categories based on signal density:

- Category 1: up to 75 signals per hour
- Category 2: up to 175 signals per hour
- Category 3: up to 300 signals per hour
- Categories 4–5: above 300 signals per hour.

Under high-intensity sailing conditions, the number of signals from information display devices (IDDs) and incoming commands increases almost two- to threefold, and correspondingly, the density of the informational flow reaches 172 ± 18.7 to 420 ± 30.4 . This justifies describing the polytone effect, caused by the need for frequent attention switching in unexpected situations, and assessing labor intensity due to this factor at 4–5 points or Class 3.2.

Such a high degree of strain is typically characteristic of the work of the captain, pilot, and, in certain cases, the watch officer during passage through straits, narrow channels, port waters, foggy conditions, coastal navigation, mooring operations, as well as for watch crews on river and high-speed vessels throughout almost the entire navigation period.

Specific conditions of navigation—such as voyage duration, vessel habitability and type, seafarers’ specialties, and the characteristics of their daily life—necessitate selecting personnel with a broad reaction norm, high adaptive capacity, strong nervous system, and a balanced excitation–inhibition of neural processes. Only such individuals possess the biological and social resources necessary to process information, including its volume and rate of inflow, which may be excessive or insufficient depending on the situation during the voyage.

Prolonged absence of proprioceptive impulses, limitation of afferent signaling and the muscular component of emotions leads to deconditioning of the body, a decrease in muscle tone and limitation of adaptive reactions. Long-term hypodynamia, according to a number of indicators

of functional and structural changes, manifests itself in the same reactions of the body that are characteristic of the state of increased load.

Table 3

Scoring Assessment of Workload Severity and Intensity in Major Professional Groups of Shipboard Specialists

Psychophysiological factors of working conditions	Professional Groups					
	Deck		Machine		Electrical	
	Navigator	Sailor	Mechanic	Motorman	Electro-mechanic	Electrician
1. Workload severity						
1. Dynamic physical load	1	2-3	2	2-3	1	2
2. Static physical load	2	2-3	2	2-3	2-3	2-3
3. Maximum weight of handled cargo	1	3	2	3	1	1
4. Duration of motor activity	1	3	2	3	1	2
5. Work pace	1	2-3	2	2	1	1
6. Work posture	1	2-3	2	3	2	2
7. Body tilts	1	3	1	2	2	2
8. Walking	1	3	1	2	2	2
9. Work-rest schedule	4	3-4	4	3-4	3-4	3-4
10. Work in PPE	1	2-3	2	3	2	3
2. Workload intensity						
11. Duration of focused observation	4-5	1-3	4-5	4-5	1-3	1-3
12. Number of critical observation objects	4	2-3	3-4	2-3	3	2-3
13. Number of informational signals	2-5	1-4	2-5	2-4	1-3	1-3
14. Number of emergency signals	3	2	3	2	2	1
15. Monotony	1-3	1-3	1-2	1-2	2-3	1-3
16. Monotonous workload	1-3	1-3	1-2	1-2	2	1-2
17. Visual strain	3	2-3	3	3	2	2
18. Blinding action	3	3	2	2	2	2
19. Hearing strain	2	1	4	4	3	3
20. Type of operator activity	4-5	1-2	4-5	3	3	2
21. Intellectual workload	4-5	2	4-5	3	4	3
22. Neuro-psychological strain	4-5	2-3	4-5	3	4	3
23. Emotional strain	3-5	2-3	4-5	3-5	4-3	3
24. Degree of higher mental function involvement	3-5	2-3	3-5	2-4	3-4	2-3
25. Desynchronization	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3
26. Danger of injury	2	3	4	4	4	4

At the same time, the inevitable change in the size and structure of skeletal and cardiac muscles, their functional denervation and the increase in total body mass are aggravated by the necessity to endure, during maintenance and ship-wide emergency and accident work, significant postural-tonic strain and peak physical loads on the trunk – 1700–3200 kg/m per hour and the shoulder girdle – 1400–2000 kg/m per hour (3–4 points).

Among enlisted personnel of the engine department, during preventive maintenance work, frequent movements within the engine room are noted, as well as forced trunk bends at an angle of up to 30 or more degrees from 50 to 120 times per shift, the weight of a single lifted load being more than 10 kg – the muscular load corresponds to the 3rd (“permissible”) category of work severity. Certain types of work cause an energy expenditure of up to 6 kcal/min, while for motormen and repair mechanics the specific weight of heavy types of work reaches 16–19% of the time, and for members of the repair team – up to 27–30%. Identical physical loads periodically arise among members of the deck department engaged in ship-wide work with non-permanent workplaces.

Elements of static load (2–3 points) were found during the performance of light in severity operator tasks of the watch service and the electrical group. At the same time, subjectively perceived muscular fatigue (in 18–37% of respondents) is associated with the need to hold the head in a tilted position for a long time, turned toward information displays. When working on the bridge and in the engine room, the muscles of the shoulder, back and legs of ship specialists are tense and remain in a state of prolonged contraction to maintain a forced posture (steering wheel, radar, information systems, etc.). For muscular relaxation and shifting of the center of gravity, watchkeepers shift from one foot to the other (69%), walk around (49%), massage the neck and limbs (9%), perform individual elements of physical exercise (11%).

Thus, despite the fact that the nature of work, lifestyle and limited living space lead to pronounced hypodynamia and hypokinesia (the number of steps per day does not exceed 2–2.5 thousand), most production operations by sailors are carried out in forced, and often inconvenient, postures. The predominance of static strain leads to rapid fatigue, and the occurrence of peak physical loads during emergency and storm conditions can lead to breakdown of adaptation, the development of pathology of the peripheral nervous system and the musculoskeletal system.

The daily work and rest schedule on board for all crew members is quite demanding (3–4 points). Ship specialists performing a stable 4-hour watch duty work no less than 9 hours (officers – 9–10) with 6–7 hours of uninterrupted sleep. Other crew members have an 8-hour work schedule. The absence of days off during the entire voyage, as well as performing administrative duties (at least 1–2 hours for officers), emergency and repair work, and training exercises, leads to the accumulation of chronic fatigue, disruption of the dynamic work stereotype, and psycho-emotional tension (PET). Today, the WHO concept regarding chronic stress is becoming central in the comprehensive approach being developed to occupational health protection. Accordingly, exposure time must be taken into account to the same extent as the intensity of harmful factors. For example, for seafarers, “time-based protection” can be implemented through limitations on years of service and early retirement, while organizational measures such as additional intra-shift rest, reduced working hours or week, or extra leave are practically meaningless under shipboard conditions.

The increase in the number and power of energy installations, the presence of open, easily and frequently accessible hazardous zones, hydro- and high-voltage electrical equipment in the engine room, in violation of safety rules, can lead to injuries with severe or fatal outcomes for members of the engine team (mechanic, motorman – 4 points) and the electrical group (electromechanic, electrician – 5 points). The probability of injury is exacerbated by noise-vibration exposure in the engine room, which contributes to progressive fatigue and erroneous actions. According to content analysis of technical documentation and professional profiles, the highest likelihood of exposure to hazardous factors for engine and electrical group personnel is caused by the following circumstances:

1. servicing rotating and moving parts of machinery and hard-to-reach equipment, as well as hot boilers and furnaces in confined spaces;

2. crowded equipment and the vertical arrangement of machinery blocks, which necessitates movement and work on 3–6 “levels” (2–6 m) with a total engine room height of up to 30 m;

3. dismantling work in hard-to-reach areas during voyage maintenance of bulky and heavy equipment, especially under time constraints during emergencies or rough seas;

4. work with pressure vessels, boilers, and cylinders;

5. the risk of electric shock due to high humidity and work on metal surfaces, mechanical and thermal damage to the network;

6. the use of personal protective equipment for the face, eyes, and respiratory system (visors, helmets, respirators, etc.), which impairs gas and heat exchange, reduces visibility and field of view, restricts freedom of movement and orientation;

7. work in areas with increased electrical hazard – presence of moisture, chemically active environments, high-voltage networks, conductive decks and bulkheads, simultaneous contact with metal parts of the hull and electrical equipment, hand-held power tools and lighting.

Conditionally hazardous zones and tasks for the deck crew include:

1. open and high-altitude passages above the deck and holds; presence of ropes, shrouds, railings, etc.;

2. high concentration of lifting and transport mechanisms and equipment during cargo handling operations on different levels of the ship;

3. performing mooring, towing, and anchoring operations; moving hatch covers and securing cargo in the dark, especially under adverse weather and rough seas;

4. simultaneous performance of various tasks on small platforms, incompatible according to safety rules;

5. the necessity for seamen (sometimes carrying cargo) to move along narrow passages, ladders, vertical and steeply inclined stairs, which may become slippery due to oil, fuel, or ice, especially in stormy and windy weather;

6. presence on upper open decks when working with radar and radio transmitters;

7. working in bulky and inconvenient protective clothing (wet or iced jackets, gloves, etc.), which restricts movement and coordination, and in adverse weather conditions often leads to difficult and erroneous actions.

Today, the issue of ship automation, maximum crew reduction, and the combination of professions has become extremely acute regarding maritime safety and injury risk. Some specialized automated ships with a deadweight of over 6,000 registered tons are operated by crews of 18–20 people, one-third of whom combine duties of the deck and engine teams. Human presence in the engine room is completely excluded. As a result, the number of watchkeepers is reduced, while the working week extends to 60–76 hours. The danger of this trend lies in the following aspects: a ship cannot constantly operate in fully automated mode – there is always a risk of engine or automation system failure. In case of breakdowns or emergencies, the small crew cannot independently handle repairs or effectively maintain the vessel’s survivability. Intensification of labor due to the combination of “heterogeneous” specialties, transfer of some management and monitoring functions of ship machinery and technical systems to the watch officer, and increased working hours and professional duties lead to cumulative fatigue, weakened attention, and slower reactions. This is exacerbated by complex hydro-meteorological conditions, equipment and automation malfunctions, passage through narrow channels under poor visibility, and high traffic density. The watchkeeping service, responsible for ship navigation, thus bears enormous responsibility for the lives of people and material assets (4–5 points, 3.2 class).

Thus, the high degree of labor intensity during long multi-month voyages, combined with the lack of psychophysiological fitness programs in the main professions of the crew, leads not only to accidents caused by hazardous factors but also to the development of chronic neurogenic pathology and specific forms of addictive behavior.

Conclusions:

Therefore, alongside medical examinations, preliminary and periodic psychophysiological examination should be implemented as a crucial preventive measure aimed at preserving sailors’ health and providing individually oriented rehabilitation (medical and socio-psychological) during off-voyage periods. Targeted medical selection and psychoprophylactic measures open the

prospect of actively managing adaptation processes under extreme sailing conditions, contributing to health preservation, reduction of psycho-emotional tension, prevention of injuries, and maritime safety.

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